

A REVIEW OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE PLATFORMS IN TEACHING PEDIATRICS

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Abstract. *The article presents current literature on the potential and use of artificial intelligence and virtual reality platforms in teaching medical students, as well as in training sessions for physicians in various specialties. It highlights the capabilities of individual educational platforms, their functionality and a sample list of practical skills, instrumental and laboratory test data used to teach diagnostic skills for a particular syndrome or disease.*

Keywords: *virtual reality, artificial intelligence, learning, practical skills, educational platforms, comparative analysis.*

Introduction. In the context of an ever-growing volume of medical information and the increasing difficulty of selecting real clinical cases, traditional teaching methods no longer always ensure a sufficiently deep analysis of certain nosological entities. Virtual reality (VR) and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies introduce a new level of interaction, enabling students to simulate a wide range of clinical situations during their training [1]. VR is a multifunctional technology that immerses the user into a fully simulated three-dimensional environment, creating a strong sense of presence through specialized equipment. AI, in turn, enhances immersion technologies by making the learning process interactive, adaptive, and personalized. It governs the behavior of virtual patients, maintaining communication, reacting to a student's actions, demonstrating characteristic symptoms, producing realistic sensations and emotional responses, and modifying the patient's condition based on correct or incorrect interventions. AI also monitors the accuracy, consistency, and effectiveness of diagnostic and therapeutic decisions, evaluates the time required for clinical reasoning, and generates variability by introducing unpredictable clinical events, possible complications, and diverse patient profiles [2]. In other words, AI transforms VR simulations from a predominantly game-like format into a comprehensive clinical training tool, where students can systematically develop both clinical reasoning and practical skills [3, 4].

Virtual Patient Platforms. The introduction of innovative technologies into medical education is expected to enhance training effectiveness, broaden access to educational resources, improve practical skill acquisition, and ultimately raise the overall quality of preparation for future healthcare professionals [5]. In response to these educational demands, numerous platforms incorporating AI and VR technologies have been developed.

One of the most widely recognized virtual patient platforms is **BodyInteract** (Take The Wind, Portugal) [6]. The primary version is presented as a touchscreen tabletop simulating a patient lying on a hospital bed, although mobile versions are also available. According to the developers, depending on the collection of scenarios, the platform may include several hundred simulated clinical situations across 30 medical specialties, such as cardiology, gastroenterology, neurology, pulmonology, endocrinology, and traumatology.

The learning algorithm is structured as follows: assessment of the general clinical picture and patient status, patient interview, physical examination, evaluation of physiological parameters,

application of the ABCDE sequence (a structured approach to prioritizing and performing clinical tasks), interpretation of laboratory and instrumental test results, formulation of a differential diagnosis, determination of treatment tactics and drug selection, prognosis assessment, and further actions such as monitoring clinical dynamics, repeating physical examinations, reassessing the patient's condition, transferring the patient to another hospital department, completing the simulation session, and evaluating the learner's performance.

Research findings indicate that small-group learning with platform-based simulations is an effective educational tool. Future studies should focus on comparing the learning outcomes of small-group, large-group, and individual instruction formats, as well as on quantitatively assessing how these modes influence the development of clinical reasoning skills [7-9].

DIMEDUS Digital Medical Education Systems (Dimedus Inc., USA) is a virtual educational platform designed for teaching a wide spectrum of clinical competencies, from basic medical, communication, and manual skills to the development of clinical reasoning across more than 20 medical specialties, including cardiology, pulmonology, gastroenterology, hematology, endocrinology, oncology, obstetrics and gynecology, and others [10]. The approximate training algorithm incorporates patient communication, initial assessment of the patient's condition, physical examination, the ability to analyze and respond to evolving clinical situations (such as emerging complications and life-threatening conditions), interpretation of laboratory and instrumental test results, treatment planning, and the execution of surgical or procedural interventions. The platform is available on mobile devices, large interactive touch panels, and VR headsets, and is supplemented by interactive theoretical lessons with 3D animation [11].

Oxford Medical Simulation (Oxford Medical Simulation Ltd., UK) is a system developed to train healthcare workers for functioning in high-risk "red zone" environments during the COVID-19 pandemic [12]. It emphasizes physical examination skills, the elicitation of complaints and medical history, the review of clinical data, and the interpretation of instrumental and laboratory test results. The platform is specifically designed to help learners build holistic clinical reasoning skills under stress. Additionally, it includes modules focused on nursing and intensive care competencies [13].

Full Code Medical Simulation (Full Code Medical Inc., USA) is a simulation platform for mobile devices, tablets, and computers that does not rely on VR technology [14]. It covers clinical cases in 31 specialties, including allergology, cardiology, dermatology, endocrinology, gastroenterology, hematology, oncology, neurology, pulmonology, otolaryngology, among others. Clinical decision-making follows a dialogue-based format: identifying complaints and medical history, applying the ABCDE algorithm, performing a general examination, gathering palpation and auscultation findings, and ordering laboratory and instrumental tests. Treatment options and diagnosis selection are provided from extensive specialty-specific lists. Despite minor technical limitations, the platform is noted for its convenience, portability, and accessibility, especially compared to more robust simulation systems used in structured educational environments. Due to its scalable and resource-efficient functionality, Full Code appears to be a promising tool for medical students, warranting further evaluation of its educational effectiveness [15].

Leonardo VR (EIDOS Ltd., Russia) is a virtual patient technology delivered through an interactive screen-table, developed for training in diagnostics, clinical decision-making, and treatment [16]. It includes approximately 60 clinical scenarios in cardiology, pulmonology, critical care, endocrinology, gastroenterology, neurology, obstetrics and gynecology, emergency medicine, and other fields. A scenario designer enables the creation of an unlimited number of

customized clinical cases, significantly expanding the system's educational potential. Functionalities include patient interviews, real-time monitoring of vital signs, general physical examination, auscultation and percussion of the heart and lungs, laboratory and instrumental testing, medication administration, and resuscitation procedures.

Virtual Patient Botkin (GEOTAR Tzifra, Russia) is an interactive educational system available on computers, tablets, and smartphones [17]. It provides clinical cases in cardiology, pulmonology, otolaryngology, endocrinology, rheumatology, and nephrology. A complete consultation is conducted through dialogue-based interaction, which includes patient interviewing (complaints, history, lifestyle), physical examination (general inspection, palpation, percussion - presented in textual format and auscultation with audio playback), assessment of laboratory and instrumental findings, analysis of specialist reports, identification of the leading syndrome and comorbidities, compilation of possible complications, selection of an ICD-10 diagnosis, treatment planning, and formulation of recommendations. The system offers both training and test modes, providing the learner with a score and percentage of correct responses upon completion.

Virtual Patient Filatov (GEOTAR Tzifra, Russia) is a pediatric modification of the Botkin platform [18]. It includes patient scenarios involving children aged 1 to 14 years across specialties such as pulmonology and allergology, cardiology, gastroenterology, rheumatology, nephrology, endocrinology, parasitology, neonatology, pediatric infectious diseases, pediatric surgery, and emergency and outpatient pediatrics (including comprehensive health assessments). Its functionality mirrors that of the Botkin system, but incorporates pediatric-specific diagnostic requirements such as immunization records, daily routines, feeding patterns, developmental reflexes, and others. Conclusions may include an assessment of physical and psychomotor development, resistance, functional status of organs and systems, and overall health condition.

Conclusion. The advantages of traditional teaching methods are unquestionable, as students ultimately interact with real patients rather than virtual models. Therefore, fully or even partially replacing bedside training with VR/AI-based learning is inappropriate and potentially unsafe, as it may foster a sense of detachment, reduced responsibility, or a game-like perception of clinical situations. Nonetheless, due to the annual increase in student enrollment and the limited number of faculty, traditional methods alone cannot ensure the development of all necessary practical competencies. A major advantage of AI and VR technologies is that they allow students to practice independently without direct instructor supervision. This makes them suitable for structured independent learning within clinical departments as well as for self-directed study during free time. Numerous studies demonstrate that VR is an effective tool for learning, practicing, and reinforcing practical skills in clinical disciplines, often improving proficiency compared to traditional instructional approaches. The identified benefits - safe skills training environments, the ability to simulate rare or complex clinical cases, increased motivation, as well as limitations such as the need for technical support and the potential high cost of content development, require thorough evaluation when integrating these technologies into medical education. A blended approach that combines innovative technologies with traditional teaching methods has the potential to enhance both the quality of theoretical instruction and the level of practical skills. Despite its high potential, widespread adoption of VR in medical education faces several challenges, including financial and technical constraints and the lack of appropriate physical space for VR infrastructure. Furthermore, successful implementation requires an adequate legal and regulatory framework. Development of VR courses also demands highly qualified interdisciplinary teams consisting of software engineers, experienced medical instructors, AI

specialists, designers, and educational methodologists. Existing shortcomings, such as technical problems or insufficient realism - can be addressed through further technological advancement.

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